

A Corpus Driven Approach: How Amy Tan Narrates The Novel “The Kitchen God’s Wife”

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Abstract

This paper attempts to study how Amy Tan narrates her novel “The Kitchen God’s Wife” using a Corpus Driven Approach. It is aimed at highlighting the use of nouns and their effects in Amy Tan’s novel. For this purpose, a corpus of Amy Tan’s novel has been compiled and analyzed with the help of Antconc software. For a detailed scrutiny, the concordance lines have been explored thoroughly. This study is a detailed analysis of lexical items along with insights that have been gathered from keyword lists and clusters to reveal how the author narrates her story. The analysis of keywords shows that the story is quantitatively dominant with the female characters and the author frequently uses time nouns to depict its setting and body nouns in her story in order to portray her characters.

Key words: Corpus Driven Approach, Antconc software, keyword lists, clusters

Introduction

Scholars who study literary texts employ various approaches such as literary criticism, practical criticism and linguistic criticism. ‘Literary criticism’ is the study, evaluation and interpretation of literary texts. ‘Practical criticism’ is a kind of criticism that analyzes specific literary works and mainly focuses on the language structure of texts rather than on the social, cultural and historical context. Another kind of criticism is ‘linguistic criticism’ which focuses on linguistic structure of text. A hybrid of linguistics and literary criticism which is concerned with the relationship between the linguistic form and meaning of a literary text is called stylistics. Corpus linguistics is the electronic analysis of language data. The combination of both disciplines is corpus stylistics, the linguistic analysis of electronically stored literary texts. Corpus linguistics is different from traditional stylistics which allows the analysis of only short texts or extracts from longer texts; corpus driven approach permits the analysis of much longer texts. This study deals with a corpus-based stylistic analysis of Amy Tan’s novel *The Kitchen God’s Wife*. The purpose of pursuing this area of study is that corpus linguistics gives both quantitative and qualitative data which quickly reveals the lexical and grammatical patterns of language and it makes it easier to detect style of the author in relation to language use. It provides new tools for studying literary text in order to gain new insights and findings.

The electronic text of *The Kitchen God’s Wife* consists of 163373 words (532 pages). The study focuses on the keyword analysis of content words, particularly ‘nouns’. The frequency range is set up to top 200 results because the occurrences of function words are abundantly found in top 100 results of the keywords list. This study investigates how the author narrates the novel through her linguistic choices in terms of a corpus driven approach.

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Aim and Objectives

The aim of this paper is to reveal how the author narrates the story in the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife* by Amy Tan in terms of corpus driven approach. The objectives of the study are:

- (1) to explore how the author narrates the story by using corpus linguistic tools such as keywords, concordance, n-grams,
- (2) to examine how the author uses nouns to present the family and social ties and the portrayal of the characters and to investigate how the author depicts setting in the novel in terms of n-grams.

Literature Review

Corpus Stylistics

Corpus in linguistics refers to a collection of electronically stored texts. Corpora are large bodies of electronic texts containing millions of words and corpus linguistics is a scholarly enterprise concerned with the compilation and analysis of corpora. So corpus stylistics which is under the scope of linguistics is a linguistic analysis of electronically stored literary texts. Corpus stylistics studies how literary effects are encoded in language by decoding linguistic patterns and their meanings in literary texts. Sinclair (1991:4) claims that the ability to examine large text corpora in a systematic manner allows access to a quality of evidence that has not been available before. The advantage of applying corpus linguistic analysis in analyzing literary texts is that it enables the researchers to analyze an extremely large body of corpora and the data yielded by the software is systematic and organized. It is therefore a quantitative approach to appreciating literary works. Starcke (2010:1) states that corpus stylistics pursues two goals: to study how meaning is encoded in language and to develop appropriate working techniques to decode these meanings, and to study the literary meanings of texts. Corpus stylistics investigates both lexis and phrase levels. The analysis of lexical items include keywords analysis and of the phrase level includes collocates, clusters, n-grams.

Summary of the novel

The novel opens with the narrative voice of Pearl Louie Brandt, The American-born daughter of a Chinese mother and a Chinese-American father, living in [San Jose, California](#). Pearl's mother, Winnie Louie, has called her to request that she and her family come to San Francisco, to attend the engagement party of Bao-Bao, her cousin. Later, Pearl receives another call from her mother telling her that her elderly Auntie Du has died, with her funeral being arranged for the day following Bao-Bao's party.

Upon her arrival in San Francisco, her Auntie Helen makes a demand: she insists that Pearl must tell Winnie that she has [multiple sclerosis](#), something which everyone else in the family knows; Helen claims that she is suffering from a malignant brain tumor and does not want to die knowing that Winnie is unaware of her daughter's illness. Helen adds that if Pearl will not tell the truth, she will do it herself. Afterwards, Helen has a similar conversation with Winnie, telling her that she must reveal the truth of her past to Pearl.

At this point the novel switches to the narrative voice of Winnie Louie, telling the story of her past. Before reaching the United States, Winnie experienced a life of turmoil and suffering: She was abandoned by her mother, a lesser wife of her father, as a young child, and did not fully understand her mother's mysterious disappearance. She was forced to live with her uncle and his two wives, never feeling as loved as her uncle's daughter, Peanut. Nevertheless, when the time came, Winnie's aunts arranged a traditional marriage for her, and her father provided a large dowry, since he was an educated and well-established man.

The marriage to Wen Fu, who first courted Peanut but transferred his attentions to Winnie when he learned of her father's wealth, turned out to be a disaster. Winnie suffered physical and mental abuse at the hands of her husband, losing many children along the way. Throughout her marriage, Winnie does many things behind the scenes that her husband takes credit for, and she likens her situation to a Chinese fable about a man who was horrible to his wife no matter how much she did for him, and yet still became known as "the [Kitchen God](#)".

It was during the [war](#) that Winnie met Jimmy Louie, Pearl's father; He was a good husband, a good father, and a minister in the Chinese Baptist Church, but he died when Pearl was a teenager, a time when Pearl became very angry. Winnie explains to Pearl that she met Jimmy Louie in China, at an American military dance. The two fell in love and he began to help escape her abusive marriage. In order to gain a divorce, the paper has to be signed by two witnesses and Grand Auntie Du and Helen agreed to sign. Wen-Fu had previously ripped up the papers from her first attempt, and Winnie went to him again to get the papers signed. At this second meeting Wen Fu raped her. Winnie explains that she has always tried to love Pearl more because she thought she might have been Wen-Fu's daughter.

After Winnie tells her story, Pearl reveals the secret of her disease. By the time the wedding of Bao-Bao comes around, mother and daughter have come to know each other better. Winnie goes into a local shop finds an altar with an unnamed goddess. The shopkeeper gives it to her for half price because it is considered bad luck. Winnie names it "Lady Sorrowfree" the wife of the Kitchen god, who has endured all, received no credit for the work she has done, and is still strong. At the end of the novel, Helen reveals that she is planning a trip to China, with Pearl, and Winnie.

Key Terms

- concordance : a list of all the occurrences of a particular search term in a corpus, presented within the context in which they occur
- keyword : a word that appears significantly statistically more frequently in a text or a corpus
- collocate : a word which occurs with the neighborhood of another word and collocation is the phenomenon in which certain words are more likely to occur in combination with other words in certain contexts
- n-gram : a recurrent string of uninterrupted word-forms which are also called clusters, chains or lexical bundles.

Research Methodology

Material

The material used in the study is the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife* written by Amy Tan, a [Chinese-American](#) author. It was first published by [G. P. Putnam's Sons](#) in 1991. The story mirrors Tan's own: the tale of Pearl, the California-born daughter of Winnie, a Chinese immigrant who fled to America to escape an abusive [traditional marriage](#) and the turmoil of war. The novel was well accepted internationally, reaching [the New York Times Best Seller list](#) in the first month of its publication, remaining there for a total of thirty eight weeks. The book went on to be included on several best sellers lists in Australia, England, Canada, Denmark, Spain and Germany.

Method

AntConc is a freeware multiplatform tool developed by Laurence Anthony (2011) for carrying out corpus linguistics research and data-driven learning. The software contains seven tools: concordance tool, concordance plot tool, file view tool, clusters (n-grams), collocates, wordlist and keyword list. This study focuses on the analysis of keywords and clusters of only nouns from top 200 results of keyword list with the highest frequency are included.

Procedures

In order to carry out the analysis, the electronic version of the novel is needed. The novel in the PDF file is created as a text file. The text *The Kitchen God's Wife* consists of 163373 word tokens (words) of 7336 word types. The practical procedures for the analysis of language use in narrating the story are as follows:

- (1) collecting data from the electronic text of *The Kitchen God's Wife* by using AntConc software to extract the keywords and n-grams/clusters,
- (2) analyzing how the author uses these keywords and n-grams/clusters to depict the setting and to portray the characters in the novel and investigating the author's narration style through these keywords and n-grams/ clusters.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the aim and objectives of the study, the following research questions are formulated:

1. How does the author narrate the story by using corpus linguistic tools such as keywords, concordance, n-grams?
2. How does the author use nouns to present the family and social ties and the portrayal of the characters?
3. How does the author depict setting in the novel in terms of n-grams?

Analysis of Data

In the corpus of Amy Tan's novel *The Kitchen God's Wife*, the most frequently occurred nouns are enlisted in the table that follows. The detail analysis of all these nouns is not feasible in the scope of this study, so the top sixteen most frequent nouns have been chosen for the analysis.

Sr. No.	Nouns	Frequency
1.	MOTHER	619
2.	WAY	383
3.	FATHER	323
4.	AUNTIE	285
5.	DAY	265
6.	HUSBAND	242
7.	MAN	238
8.	GIRL	226
9.	AUNT	217
10.	FACE	200
11.	BABY	152
12.	WOMAN	152
Sr. No.	Nouns	Frequency
13.	WIFE	146
14.	HEAD	142
15.	EYES	137
16.	NIGHT	123

Table No. 1: Keywords indicating the top most frequent nouns in the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife*

Analyzing Keywords indicating family ties and social ties of the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife*

In keyword analysis, the frequency limit of keywords is set to top 200 results because of the abundant occurrences of function words in top 100 results of keyword lists and only nouns are collected from the results and will be analyzed in order to indicate the family ties and social ties. The keywords associated with family ties and social ties are shown in the following table.

Sr.No.	Keywords	Frequency
1.	MOTHER	619
2.	FATHER	323
3.	AUNTIE	258
4.	HUSBAND	242
5.	MAN	238
6.	GIRL	226
7.	AUNT	217
8.	WOMAN	152
9.	BABY	152
10.	WIFE	146

Table No. 2: Keywords indicating family ties and social ties of the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife*

As seen in table, the most frequent noun denoting the family is 'MOTHER' which appears 619 times in the novel describing the mother-daughter relationship between the character-narrator and her mother as seen in the following lines:

<p>THE SHOP OF THE GODS Whenever gument. "Pearl ah, have to go, no choice se days "the Louies" really refers only to arriage; Auntie Helen's first husband was is third marriage." "Fourth engagement</p>	<p>my mother talks to me, she begins the conversation as my mother said when she phoned last week. After sev my mother and me, since my father is dead and my br my mother 's brother, who died long before I was born. my mother said. "Last one he didn't marry, broken off</p>
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Since many characters are involved in the novel, a detailed analysis has been done and it shows that 'my mother' 496 times, 'your mother' 48 times, 'her mother' 31 times, 'his mother' 17 times, 'the mother' 19 times and 'own mother' 8 times are displayed in the list.

Although 'father' is the breadwinner, the head of the family and the decision-maker of the family in Chinese culture, the word 'father' is not used as frequently as 'mother' because it can be assumed that the main character of the novel is close to her mother, not her father. The keyword nouns 'husband' (242 times) and 'man' (238 times) are used more than the nouns 'wife' (146 times) and 'woman' (152 times). This makes the sense that the use of male nouns 'husband' and 'man' frequently occur over their female counterpart since the novel is about the experiences of the mother and daughter found in their conversations and it is mostly related to their close ones, not to their whole circle.

us by blood, just by marriage; Auntie Helen's first husband was my mother's brother, who died long before
Doug Cheu, who went to medical school with my husband ,Phil Brandt, and in fact, she was the one who in
ce, many years ago, I bought a special fish for my husband for Jimmy Louie. Oh, how I loved him! The fish

t this fish would taste in Jimmy's mouth, how my husband would know this was a special fish, a lucky fish, ty as me. Around the same time I married my first husband, she had a wedding contract to a rich banking fa marry a good man, a man named Lin, for my first husband. I married the wrong one instead, a man named

The keyword ‘baby’ can be seen frequently used in the novel. By looking at the concordance lines using ‘baby’ (152 times), it cannot be argued that mothers love and value their offsprings rather than fathers. It is also found out that the narrator has experienced the sorrowful loss of her babies in her life according to the following lines:

by, which is what bao-bao means, "precious baby. " Later, we kept calling him that because he e to be careful," I said. "I am going to have a baby. He frowned. And just like that, he did not b hine to make a good living for myself and my baby. "She took my hands and squeezed them."Th l one, and that's when I started to cry. If this baby had been born in Shanghai. If this baby had fort winning out over hardship. I loved that baby right from the start. She had Mochou's same o see me until two days later, after I had the baby another girl. So the first time I saw my baby, big. And right away, I wanted to fight for my baby, to protect him from this curse. After everyo

The keywords that are associated with social ties can be seen as “auntie and aunt” in top 200 results. These are used among relatives as well as in social situations. But, the noun ‘uncle’ is not found in top 200 list.

eryone twenty-percent discount." My mother and	Auntie	Helen co-own Ding Ho Flower Shop on Ross
n. Although my mother suspected it was because	Auntie	Helen always urged her customers to buy the
ns." The register is broken. When my mother and	Auntie	Helen first bought the store and its fixtures, th
as the crybaby who always wailed the minute my	Aunt	and uncle walked in the door, claiming we oth
o death!" Everyone roared with laughter, and Old	Aunt	quickly slapped my hands to make me stop. "
ind of person Gung-gung would have hated. New	Aunt	said she knew all about him, because after my

Further down the list, AUNTIE, HUSBAND, MAN, GIRL, AUNT, WOMAN and WIFE are found. The total occurrence of female nouns, mother, auntie, girl, aunt, woman and wife, is much greater than the male nouns; father, husband, and man. Thus, it can be assumed that there is a great dominance of female characters over male characters.

5.2. Analyzing Keywords indicating ‘Time’ in the novel *The Kitchen God’s Wife*

The keywords that are associated with the time in the top 200 list are ‘day’ and ‘night’. These words indicate ‘duration of a situation’ (how long) and ‘indication of time’ (exact time) set in the novel. The occurrence of these nouns in different use can be seen in the following table:

Sr. No.	Keyword	Duration	Indication	Total
1.	DAY	22	243	265
2.	NIGHT	14	109	123

Table No. 3: Keywords indicating ‘Time’ in the novel *The Kitchen God’s Wife*

The total frequency of the keywords denoting indication of time (352) for both ‘day’ and ‘night’ is significantly much more than duration. It is inferred that the narrator wants to indicate the time exactly at which the characters experienced different situations throughout their life rather than how long they encountered.

t, for more than twenty-five years, ever since the day of my father's funeral. I was fourteen, full of an should not ask for more. I believed this until the day a man named Lin showed up at our same church om can't wait | to be stung by a man." That hot day at the church in Fresno, when I heard I this wor d I did not ask her any questions. On the fourth day I went downstairs by myself. As I already told y Peanut, her family, and of course, me. The next day was the new year. Everyone pretended to be hap k-and-white TV set, that sort of thing. Late that night she died of an undetected concussion. Helen h different until more than ten years later, on the night before my wedding to the wrong man. That's w our bed. But then San Ma said to me, "Later at, night you should do a small wash again." And she did "Peanut said. Two nights later, on my wedding night I was scared. When my husband took off his cl

Analyzing Keywords portraying the characters in the novel *The Kitchen God’s Wife*

Analyzing Keywords ‘way’

The second most frequent use of noun in top 200 frequency list is the keyword ‘way’ which the author uses for 383 times in her novel. In the novel, the character narrates her experience in detail in order to arouse the curiosity of the readers by using the clusters ‘the way’ (106 times), ‘that way’ (58 times), ‘this way’ (51 times), ‘the same way’ (51 times), ‘a way’ (35 times), ‘no other way’ (10 times), ‘any other way’ (10 times). In order to describe her experience in detail, the character uses ‘the way’, ‘that way’ and ‘this way’.

gry marks. I was happy and sad all at once, the way you feel when you listen to old songs you have he firmness of her hand when she held mine, the way she could peel an apple all in one long curly pie mand things. She was not strict with me, not the way some mothers can be. She was perhaps even m when I heard my mother and father talking that way I was scared. They were not shouting, but both ust bad classical stories that make me think this way There was a reason why she had to be. She was

In order to highlight that her life does not change very much throughout her life, the character uses the phrase “the same way” (41 times) in her conversation as in the following:

,pretending to be shy. Every Sunday was the same way . Only, that Sunday turned out to be very hot,
 very good at all, maybe that's why I was the same way . She said my mother had a fighting temper,
 true!" Old Aunt burst in right away. "It's the same way with me. I have stomach pains, all the time,
 then, soon after that, your brother acted the same way Wild! He shouted the same words, only this

The author also employs 35 times of using "a way" for the purpose of portraying the character who is always struggling to find a solution in difficult situations. This can be seen in the following lines:

I do not die soon, then maybe I can find a way to escape. Around that time, Hulan started to ch
 not fix those windows. Later I even found a way to get back my mother's room for my own. Whe
 thinking I might kill myself if I did not find a way out of my marriage soon." "I have had these sa
 now I was crying. "That's why I must find a way to leave my marriage. I do not expect you to for

Analyzing Keywords 'face'

Another keyword from the top 200 list is 'face' which occurs 200 times in the text of the novel. The author uses these words collocate with the adjectives in the text. By examining these lines, it can be said that the character always pays attention to or examines her mother's mood and mind whenever she meets her mother. However, she and her mother are not of the same mind and she never neglects her mother. It can be said that the character loves and respect her mother as shown in the following lines:

said that, my mother looked at me with a blank face and absolute silence. And after that, she did stop c
 ne of them says in a Texas drawl. My mother's face instantly cheers, and she nods, waving them in. "C
 ew Year." She looks at me with a determined face And now I want to shake her, tell her to stop play
 nvy her. She did not know that the shimmering face smiling back at her was her own reflection. At th
 scolded me for. And then I would wait for her face to turn red when she and all the family and guests

Some other phrases which are used to describe the actions of the other characters are 'wash her face', 'rubbed half her face' 'put powder on her face'. To describe the appearance of the characters, the phrases 'not like face of' and 'a face that was' are used as seen in the followings:

k hair, his tricky eyebrows, his smooth, lying face his clever mouth. I had not seen him for over for
 is skin was smooth and light-colored, not like face of someone who worked outdoors all day long. Y
 other admired in herself: big eyes, light skin, a face that was neither too broad nor too thin, small lips,

Analyzing Keywords ‘eyes’

The next keyword that is associated with the character is ‘eyes’, which is used 137 times in the novel. Looking through the eyes of a person, his/her mind or feeling can be sought. In this way, the writer uses the word ‘eyes’ collocates with descriptive adjectives in portraying her characters. This can be seen in the following lines:

her silly ways. She was staring at me with critical eyes. She asked me if I had made the dress I was wearing Fu must have seen my thoughts with his bad eyes because right then he reached over and slapped me. He searched constantly for my mother with fearful eyes. He was so unlike what my father had once been. "Addy?" He looks up with those helpless searching eyes. And when he sees me, he gives a small startled look. The left was so short. But then I looked again. Her eyes were clear. She did not smile or cry. She did not

Analyzing Keywords ‘head’

The keyword ‘head’ is employed for 142 times in various ways in the novel. Characters show their respect to their elders by bowing their heads. It can be seen as a Chinese custom in the following lines:

in my face and hated me. I bowed my head "Daughter," he suddenly said, "you should in you are wrong. Kneel down. Bow your head and beg me to forgive you. Kneel down!" He bowed to my aunties carefully, keeping my head bowed in a respectful manner. I heard them te

In the novel, the use of body noun ‘head’ collocates with the verb ‘pat’ and ‘tap’ is found when the relationship between the family members is shed light on, showing their love with each other as shown in the following lines:

"And that's how I knew," she says, tapping her head sounding triumphant. God touched his finger could finally leave. But instead she patted my head Syin ke, " she said, "you're already so big." She as not the kind of grandmother who patted my head and told me I was pretty. She was the big boss

Another collocation with the keyword is ‘shake’ which is more frequently used in the novel. By looking at these expressions, it is found that characters always shake their heads to refuse or to deny or to be against to do something instead of saying ‘no’.

make the wreaths. Why are you shaking your head ? This is true!" Her face becomes more serious s. "Say them!" he shouted again. I shook my head and began to cry. And then he became tender g, to your husband's parents?" She shook her head quickly. "They don't want me, I don't want th ? he asked in Chinese. I smiled and shook my head "Still I know enough English to tell. To my ey

The keyword ‘head’ is also used as the abstract noun ‘mind’ which can be seen with the collocates such as ‘thought’, ‘question’, ‘words’, ‘picture’ and ‘a place’

tunity. My mother had put those thoughts in my head .Right after I announced I had been chosen ov

piece of gossip making another question in my head .If she was dead, why did they hold no funera
 en I no longer wanted to hear her words in my head I searched for something to do. I opened a dra
 orn by carefree girl. So with this picture in my head I began to cut my cloth. I imagined myself as t
 those excuses could find a place to rest in my head And instead, I could see Wen Fu driving along

Analyzing N-grams/ Clusters with the highest frequency

In this study, only n-grams with the highest frequency are analyzed. They indicate the setting of the novel: place and time. The following table shows the n-grams that occur in the text of *The Kitchen God's Wife*.

Sr. No.	N-grams/ Clusters	Frequency
1.	6-gram	6
2.	5-gram	21
3.	4-gram	24

Table No. 4: N-grams/ Clusters in the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife*

6- grams indicating setting of the novel

The 6-gram with the highest frequency of occurrence is the prepositional phrase 'to the side of the road' which appears 6 times in the novel. The dynamic verbs 'stumble', 'push' and 'point' show how the characters acted at a certain place.

ing, blood streaming out. He stumbled to the side of the road before falling into a ditch, his four legs
 bus kept driving, pushing all that misery to the side of the road. My stomach ached to see them. Those of
 further instructions to the driver, pointing to the side of the road Sure enough, the bus gave a big groan an

5-gram depicting the setting of the novel

The 5-gram with the highest frequency of occurrence is 'at the end of the' that appears 21 times in the novel. As seen in above concordance lines, it is followed by nouns such as the story, day, meal, show, summer, building, and telegram thereby forming prepositional phrases that are associated with the depiction of the setting: place and time.

At the end of the the story, my mother exclaimed, "Nonse
 ling back at her was her own reflection.
 r feet. That's what he did, exactly that. At the end of the day when Peanut complained that her fe
 ore than ten dumplings were left over. At the end of the meal\x97just four left! What a good din
 Gao were watching a monkey dancing. At the end of the show, they threw two coppers on the gro
 same thing." So we left for Yangchow at the end of the summer, only a few weeks after the war
 . Everyone shared the kitchen located at the end of the building, as well as the heated bathhouse
 ick the right number of urgent words. At the end of the telegram to Wen Fu's sister, I added, "Hu

4-gram depicting the setting of the novel

The 4-gram that occurs with the highest frequency of 24 times in the text is ‘in front of the’ as seen in above concordance lines. The 4-gram is used with nouns such as “booth, casket, family, restaurant, pews, truck, shopkeepers and porcelain to indicate the setting of the story. The verbs used with the 4-gram such as ‘sold, kneeled, saw, run, got into and standing’ are portraying what the characters are doing in particular places.

t me and Danru the next day at the harbor,	in front of the	booth that sold tickets to Tsungming Island.
esses perched on her emotionless waxy face.	In front of the	casket is a long, low table overflowing food
bed, very still. Meanwhile, Ha-bu kneeled	in front of the	family altar and prayed in front of her dead
hotel. So we walked across the street. And	in front of the	restaurant we saw a giant wooden tub. And
rguing, I tell myself. What's done is done.	in front of the	pews is a large picture of Grand Auntie. It lo
the port, they saw my uncle stand up, run	in front of the	truck, waving both hands: Go back, go back.
New Aunt and I got into loud arguments	in front of the	shopkeepers over who would pay. Every d
ng smiled big. So did Helen. I was standing	in front of the	porcelain statues: Buddha, Goddess of Mer

Findings and Discussion

Family ties and social ties in the novel

The analysis of key words, collocates clusters, n-grams show that nouns denoting family ties and social ties is most frequently used and the story is quantitatively dominant with female characters. Times nouns are used to point out ‘the duration of a situation’ and ‘the exact time’ and the body nouns are to portray ‘the behavior, action, and feeling of characters’.

In the analysis of nouns enlisted in the top 200 items, the most frequent choice of words are ‘mother’ and ‘father’. Although ‘father’ is the dominant figure in a Chinese family, the use of the word ‘father’ is less than that of ‘mother’ to highlight the character-narrator who has a very close affinity with her mother and is also an influential figure in her life.

But the key words ‘husband’ and ‘man’ are used more repeatedly than the words ‘wife’ and ‘women’ to present how the two female characters, mother and daughter, are engaged in their conversation about ‘marriage’. The analysis of keyword ‘baby’ shows how much the narrator’s mother within embedded story loves and values her baby because she has tolerated being cruelly treated by her first husband for the sake of her baby. The keywords ‘aunty’ and ‘aunt’ can be seen in the novel to show how she deals with female characters.

Therefore, it is found that the author employed the female characters more than male nouns when she presents the family ties and social ties of the characters in the novel. In this aspect, the readers may have a glimpse of the author’s real image (femisit) and reflection from what she has done. As to her biography, she has been a member of Women and Memory Forum (NGO) where she has been enthusiastically participated in internationally sponsored gender training programmes since 1998. She may foreground the traditional Chinese culture (the identity of female oppression by male), being backgrounded by the setting of California. She seems to point out the Chinese culture and tradition on the western land (America).

Based on the family and social ties, the relationship between mother and daughter, women’s dilemmas in identifying themselves as mothers or wives, the effects of cultural items on women’ lives are closely and clearly depicted in the frame story and in the embedded story.. **Depiction of setting: time in the novel *The Kitchen God’s Wife***

In the analysis of the depiction of the setting, it is found that the most significant choice of words is the use of time nouns, 'day' and 'night'. These words describe 'the duration of a situation' and 'the indication of the time' set in the novel. They show that the author indicate where the story takes place exactly and frequently rather than the characters' actions. In analyzing the n-grams, the 6-gram with the highest frequency is "to the side of the road" is used to indicate where the actions of the characters take place, the 5-gram, 'at the end of the' is used to narrate both where and when the story take place and the 4-gram 'in front of the' is employed to set the place with the concrete nouns 'booth', 'casket', 'family', 'restaurant', 'shopkeepers' and 'statue'.

Thus, after analyzing the depiction of setting with both keywords and n-grams, the words and phrases that have clear descriptive meaning frequently occur throughout the story. The use of these words shows the author's prominent ability to depict the story to be able to make the readers see where and when the story takes place.

Portrayal of characters in the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife*

In analyzing the second most frequently used keyword 'way', the author uses it with the determiners 'the', 'this' and 'that' to describe how the characters experience their daily life problems. The phrase, 'the same way' is used many times to show the character's same unpleasant situations happen again and again in her life with the collocates 'very hot', 'pain', 'fighting temper' and 'wild'. The author also employs the phrase 'a way' followed by infinitives 'to escape' 'to get back', 'to leave' in order to portray the character who always struggles with difficult situation. The keywords (body parts, 'face', 'eyes' and 'head') show that the author portrays her character as a girl who does not go along with her mother, but she always checks her mother's mood and feeling shown in her face and eyes. Other characters are also portrayed by using the keyword 'eye' collocates with descriptive adjectives 'critical', 'bad' 'helpless', 'fearful' and 'helpless'. The keyword 'head' is used to show the actions of the characters to pay respect, to show love and care, and to point out the refusal or denial of the characters. Therefore, it can be said that the authors uses the nouns of body parts to portray her character's feeling and actions.

Conclusion

This paper attempts to examine how the author narrates the novel *The Kitchen God's Wife* by Amy Tan. This paper reveals how the characters are portrayed and the setting is depicted through the author's choice of words by using the corpus linguistic tools: keywords, concordances, collocates and n-grams/clusters.

The calculation of the keywords, and clusters are performed with the help of the Antconc software. The frequency limit of keyword is set to top 200 and the n-grams to the highest. The analysis of how Amy Tan narrates the novel in terms of corpus driven approach is going to answer the research questions adopted above.

To answer the first research question, the top 200 keywords that are associated with the characters and setting are analyzed in lexical items. These keywords act so as to give information on certain time in which the events of the story are set as background. When combined with collocates and clusters, they indicate not only the setting but also certain situation of the characters in a particular time. In addition, the use of these collocates and clusters directly reflect the situation of the character. In this novel, there are two main character narrators: a woman and her mother were portrayed as the characters who were immigrant Chinese women living in California had nostalgic memories of its food and landscapes. Mother's narration offer "secret" life story to her daughter forms the core of the novel. Through the challenges of her life in wartime China, she replaces insecurity, dependence, and self-deprecation with peace of mind, self-assurance, and independence. For the second question, the author employed the female characters more than male nouns when she presents the family ties and social ties of the characters in the novel.

As to the third question, the most frequent found n-grams: 6-gram, "to the side of the road", 5-gram, "at the end of the" and 4-gram "in front of the" reveals the exact time and location of the places to portray

the characters actions. Therefore, corpus driven approach is a both qualitative and quantitative approach which could be applied in studying the style of long literary works especially novels.

A Brief Biography of Amy Tan

Amy Tan was born on February 19, 1952, in Oakland, California, She was the second of three children and the only daughter of John Tan and Daisy Tu Ching Tan. John was a Beijing-born electrical engineer and volunteer Baptist minister, and Daisy was an industrial nurse and medical technician from Shanghai. The Tans had immigrated to California in the late 1940s, when post-war China was remodeling its society to fit its concept of communism. Amy Tan gave little thought to her Chinese relatives or to her mother's first marriage prior to her emigration from China. Because she was brought up as an American, Amy challenged parental authority, yet met John and Daisy Tan's expectations of high achievement by studying piano and excelling in science and math. Amy's emotional rootlessness led her to distance herself from Daisy, who chose Amy's careers--concert pianist and physician. Family relationships were severely strained by two agonizingly slow deaths--in 1967, Amy's seventeen-year-old brother, Peter, and in 1968, her fifty-four-year-old father, John--both victims of brain tumors. Amy's normal adolescent stresses, heightened by intense grief, pushed her into serious rebellion. Daisy Tan felt it necessary to leave California, so the family moved to Montreux, Switzerland, where Amy and her younger brother John were enrolled in a private school. Despite the foreign setting, Amy's rebelliousness flared up and she enjoyed a brief flirtation with a German involved in crime and drugs before her mother helped the police take him into custody in a risky trap at the border. When the family returned to San Francisco, Amy's scholarships and part-time work at a pizzeria paid her tuition at Linfield, a small Baptist college in McMinnville, Oregon. She pursued a medical degree on her way to a career in neurosurgery, a choice that met Daisy's standards. Amy's need to rebel and to shock her mother lessened after she gave up scruffy overalls, stopped dating hippies, and settled on Lou DeMattei, a pre-law student and likely husband material. No longer certain she wanted to be a doctor, Amy switched majors and received a degree in English in 1973, followed by an M.A. in linguistics from San Jose State and groundwork for a doctorate at the University of California at Berkeley. In 1974, she left graduate school, married Lou, a tax attorney, and settled in a San Francisco condominium.

Four years later, after Daisy returned from a trip to China, Amy and her mother patched up their differences as adults--woman to woman--having survived the worst of their alienation. For the first time, Amy Tan could acknowledge the double strands of Chinese and American traditions embellishing her past. As an employee of the Alameda County Association for Retarded Citizens, Amy worked as a language consultant to the mentally handicapped before becoming a journalist in 1979. For three years, she wrote and edited news, and then launched and helped publish a professional journal, *Emergency Room Reports*. She began penning flimsy, imitative works based on popular fiction; the stories received a steady response of rejection notices. At the Squaw Valley Community of Writers workshop, she came under the influence of award-winning writer and feminist mentor Molly Giles. With further encouragement from agent Sandra Dijkstra, Tan began writing articles and short fiction for *Atlantic Monthly*, *FM*, *Glamour*, *Grazia*, *Ladies' Home Journal*, *Life*, *McCall's*, *Publishers Weekly*, *Threepenny Review*, *San Francisco Focus*, *Seventeen*, and *Short Story Review*. She also worked on novels, including historical fiction, and polished "Endgame," the complex short story begun at Squaw Valley that later formed a pivotal episode in *The Joy Luck Club*, a blended narrative about four Chinese-American women and their mothers. A skilled raconteur capable of juggling wit, insight, and pathos within a single unified scene, Tan excels in oral tradition and complex emotional involvements. These skills, as first reflected in *The Joy Luck Club*, earned her a Commonwealth Club gold award, the Bay Area Book Reviewers award for best fiction, an American Library Association citation for best book for young adults, and nominations for the National Book Critics Circle's best novel and for the *Los Angeles Times'* best book of 1989. Tan sold the paperback rights to *The Joy Luck Club* to G. P. Putnam's Ivy Books for \$1.23 million, and the work has since been translated and distributed in seventeen languages. In 1993, Wayne Wang directed the Disney studio's screen version, which was co-produced by Oliver Stone and co-scripted by Amy Tan and Ron.

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References

- Mahlberg, M. (2005). *English General Nouns: A Corpus theoretical approach*. Liverpool: Johns Benjamin Publishing Company.
- Meyer, C.F. (2004). *English Corpus Linguistics: An introduction*. Boston: University of Massachusetts.
- Sinclair, J. (1991). *Corpus, Concordance, Collocation*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Starcke, B. (2011). *Corpus Linguistics in Literary Analysis*: London and New York: Continuum International Publishing Group.